

Alkaloids of *Alstonia scholaris*

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Abstract : Picrinine, strictamine and nareline has been isolated from the fruit pods of *Alstonia scholaris* and their structure established by various spectral data. This is the first report of these alkaloids in *A. scholaris* fruit pods.

Keywords : *Alstonia scholaris*, Apocynaceae, indole alkaloids, picrinine, strictamine, nareline.

Introduction

Alstonia scholaris R.Br. (Apocynaceae) is a tall evergreen tree widely cultivated through out India. It is found in abundance in Bengal, Jammu, Southern India and also in Burma, Ceylon, Malaya and Philippines. In the Indian System of Medicine, it is used for the treatment of fever, malaria, dysentery, ulcer and skin diseases. It is also used in reducing blood sugar and as a bitter tonic^{1,2}. A number of indole alkaloids have earlier been reported from this plant³. The present study deals with the isolation of three known indole alkaloids, picrinine (1), strictamine (2) and nareline (3) from the fruit pods of *A. scholaris*. These are the first report of these alkaloids in fruit pods of *A. scholaris*.

Results and discussion

Chromatographic resolution of the crude basic fraction of the methanolic extract of the fruit pods of *A. scholaris* yielded indole alkaloids picrinine (1), strictamine (2) and nareline (3) which were identified by direct comparison of their physical and spectral data with the literature values and by direct comparison with authentic samples.

The structures of these alkaloids were further sub-

stantiated by two dimensional NMR spectra (COSY and HETCOR). Each hydrogen couples with its neighboring hydrogen in its COSY NMR and with the carbon with which it is attached in HETCOR NMR.

Experimental

Plant material : The fruit pods of *A. scholaris* were collected from Banaras Hindu University campus, Varanasi, India and identified by Dr. N. K. Dubey, Department of Botany, Banaras Hindu University. A specimen sample is kept in the department. The fruit pods were taken for the present study.

Extraction and isolation : Dried fruit pods (2 kg) were powdered and repeatedly extracted with MeOH (10 L) by percolation at 25 °C. On removal of the solvent, the methanolic extract afforded a brown gummy mass (110 g) which was stirred mechanically with 7% aqueous citric acid. The aqueous acidic solution was separated and basified with ammonium hydroxide and extracted several times with chloroform (2 L). The combined CHCl₃ extract on evaporation furnished the mixture of crude bases (2.5 g). The crude basic fraction was chromatographed over a SiO₂ gel column and the eluets from CHCl₃, CHCl₃-MeOH (25 : 1) and (20 : 1) after purification by prep. TLC with solvent system CHCl₃-MeOH (1 : 1) and

Note

crystallization from MeOH furnished respectively picrinine⁴ (12 mg) (1) as colorless needles, R_f 0.85 (CHCl₃-MeOH, 1 : 1), strictamine⁴ (10 mg) (2), as colorless granules, R_f 0.75 (CHCl₃-MeOH, 1 : 1), nareline⁵ (8 mg) (3) as colorless granules, R_f 0.65 (CHCl₃-MeOH, 1 : 1).

Picrinine (1) : Compound 1, colorless needles, m.p. 225–227 °C; UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) nm : 235 (4.01) and 286 (3.80); $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ –42° (c 0.25, CHCl₃); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3350, 1740, 1620; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.50 (3H, dd, J 2, 5 Hz, H-18), 1.86 (1H, dd, J 2, 11 Hz, H-14 β), 2.14 (1H, m, H-14 α), 2.25 (1H, dd, J 2, 11 Hz, H-6 β), 2.46 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-16), 3.10 (1H, d, J 12.5 Hz, H-21 β), 3.30 (1H, br d, J 12.5 Hz, H-15), 3.42 (1H, d, J 11 Hz, H-6 α), 3.60 (1H, br d, J 3.5 Hz, H-3), 3.66 (3H, s, -COOMe), 3.78 (1H, m, H-21 α), 4.82 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-5), 5.40 (1H, br q, J 5 Hz, H-19), 6.78 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, H-12), 6.80 (1H, dt, J 5.5, 1 Hz, H-10), 7.10 (1H, dt, J 5.5, 1 Hz, H-11), 7.14 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, H-9); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 106.25 (C-2), 51.78 (C-3), 87.35 (C-5), 46.36 (C-6), 51.98 (C-7), 135.20 (C-8), 125.97 (C-9), 120.80 (C-10),

127.94 (C-11), 110.57 (C-12), 147.53 (C-13), 25.99 (C-14), 31.06 (C-15), 51.46 (C-16), 12.73 (C-18), 120.3 (C-19), 136.31 (C-20), 40.58 (C-21), 51.16 (COOMe), 172.4 (-COOMe); MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (relative intensity, %) : 338.1632 (55) [M⁺] (HRMS, C₂₀H₂₂N₂O₃, calcd. for. 338.1632), 320 (30), 279 (20), 261 (19), 239 (100), 234 (18).

Strictamine (2) : Compound 2, colorless granules, m.p. 113–114 °C; UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) nm : 218 (4.20) and 264 (3.70); $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ +95° (c 0.25, CHCl₃); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 1732, 1622, 1600; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.53 (3H, d, J 7.91 Hz, H-18), 1.73 (1H, dd, J 10, 2.5 Hz, H-6 α), 1.97 (1H, m, H-14 β), 2.06 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, H-16), 2.61 (1H, m, H-5 β), 2.67 (1H, m, H-6 β), 2.72 (1H, m, H-5 α), 3.11 (1H, d, J 12.5 Hz, H-22 β), 3.48 (1H, br s, H-15), 3.69 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.70 (1H, dd, J 10.5, 4 Hz, H-14 α), 4.04 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz, H-21 α), 4.68 (1H, br d, J 4 Hz, H-3), 5.48 (1H, q, J 5 Hz, H-19), 7.15 (1H, dt, J 5.5, 1 Hz, H-10), 7.32 (1H, dt, J 5.5, 1 Hz, H-11), 7.41 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, H-9), 7.61 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, H-12); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ :

190.77 (C-2), 55.05 (C-3), 51.91 (C-5), 35.94 (C-6), 56.05 (C-7), 137.74 (C-8), 123.45 (C-9), 125.60 (C-10), 128.16 (C-11), 120.96 (C-12), 155.47 (C-13), 33.35 (C-14), 32.36 (C-15), 55.26 (C-16), 12.94 (C-18), 120.08 (C-19), 146.18 (C-20), 53.59 (C-21), 51.60 (COOCH₃), 171.62 (COOCH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV) *m/z* (relative intensity, %) : 322.1678 (100) [M⁺] (HRMS, C₂₀H₂₂N₂O₂, calcd. for : 322.1681), 321 (70), 291 (10), 264 (15), 263 (60), 234 (24), 220 (9), 180 (23).

Nareline (3) : Compound 3, colorless granules, m.p. 271–273 °C; UV λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) nm : 256 (3.77); [α]_D²⁵ –75° (c 0.58, pyridine); IR ν_{max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 1731, 1626, 1599; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 1.64 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, H-18), 2.12 (2H, br s, H-14), 2.48 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H-16), 3.24 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H-15), 3.44 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H-6), 3.66 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.88 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, H-5), 3.96 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H-21), 4.40 (1H, m, H-3), 5.76 (1H, q, *J* 6 Hz, H-19), 6.61 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, OH-5), 7.28 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, H-10), 7.42 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, H-11), 7.68 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-9 and H-12); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 184.25 (C-2), 61.94 (C-3), 99.44 (C-5), 55.66 (C-6), 54.87 (C-7), 139.91 (C-8), 120.41 (C-9), 125.02 (C-10), 125.48 (C-11), 128.80 (C-

12), 157.64 (C-13), 34.13 (C-14), 31.0 (C-15), 52.55 (C-16), 12.36 (C-18), 121.55 (C-19), 131.50 (C-20), 64.85 (C-21), 51.74 (COOCH₃), 171.05 (COOCH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV) *m/z* (%) : 352.1432 (28) [M⁺] (C₂₀H₂₀N₂O₄, HRMS, calcd. for 352.1422), 324 (29), 323 (80), 307 (22), 293 (12), 266 (30), 265 (100), 247 (21), 206 (20).

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